

DESIGN, ANALYSIS AND TESTING OF CFRP CRUCIFORM SPECIMENS

by

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ABSTRACT

There is a need for an effective flat cruciform shaped specimen to investigate the biaxial strength properties of fibre reinforced composites. In this study, various fabrication methods of such a specimen are presented and discussed. The effect of the geometrical parameters and the material characteristics on: a) the mechanical response of the specimen, especially the test area, b) the homogeneity and magnitude of the stress (strain) field induced in the gauge area, c) the overall performance of the specimens for tests up to failure is investigated.

Two fabrication methods have been proven satisfactory to produce flat cruciform shaped specimens. Numerical analysis and experimental results have shown that homogeneous stress (strain) field develops over the major part of the circular gauge area. High stress levels have been attained in the tested sublaminates, however specimens suffered from premature failure due to high shear stress developing in the fillet joining the arms.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The use of multiaxial strength criteria have not been proven satisfactory and many of them require material properties derived from multiaxial tests which are rare and often unreliable. Multiaxial testing of anisotropic materials, such as advanced thermoset and thermoplastic composites used for aircraft structures, necessitates the development of specimen designs. There is a need for an effective flat cruciform shaped specimen to evaluate the cyclic and static strength of fibre reinforced composites subjected to biaxial states of stress. Such a specimen will also provide experimental data that may be used to verify existing strength criteria or develop new ones. This study is part of a programme whose main objective is to investigate the behaviour of laminated composites under biaxial stress conditions and to develop analytical tools and techniques for predicting, monitoring and controlling their behaviour.

Flat cruciform specimens are widely used for biaxial testing of materials, metals and alloys [1-3] as well as polymer matrix composites [4-8]. Thin walled tubular specimens [9-11] may also be used but suffer from several limitations when testing fibre reinforced composites such as fabrication and load introduction problems. The specimen geometry illustrated in Figure 1 was adopted for this study. It is based on a geometry developed by Wilson and White [3] for metallic materials and on a preliminary numerical investigation using a NASTRAN finite element model onto the effects of the main geometrical parameters (GAD, FR, HFL, HAW, Tg/Ta) and stacking sequence of the arm reinforcement laminates.

This investigation was focused on the question whether a biaxial stress-strain field develops in the central gauge area of the specimen and on the effect of the GAD and the type of arm reinforcement laminates onto both the magnitude and homogeneity of this field. The purpose of this investigation was also to obtain experimental data to compare with numerical results obtained from the finite element model that may serve to further optimize the specimen.

Eight cruciform shaped specimens were fabricated with a central gauge area either of 63,5 or 76,2 mm in diameter and having the arm reinforcement laminates of different characteristics. The specimens were fully instrumented with strain gauges and were loaded in biaxial tension up to different load levels. Results from the NASTRAN finite element (FE) analysis are given for comparisons with the experimental results.

2.0 CRUCIFORM SPECIMENS

The specimens were fabricated in HERCULES AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy with the arm reinforcement laminates (top and bottom) either of the same material system or in E-glass/epoxy. A $[0/90]_s$ cross-ply laminate was to be tested under biaxial loading conditions. Characteristics of the eight specimens are given in Table 1. The fillet radius (FR) and the arm width ($2 \cdot \text{HAW}$) were 25,4 mm and 76,2 mm respectively and were kept constant for this investigation. The ratio of the thickness of the gauge area to the thickness of the arms (T_g/T_a) varied from 0,13 to 0,43.

Figure 1. Specimen geometry and reference axes.

Table 1. Description of the eight specimens.

Specimen	GAD(mm)	T_g/T_a	Reinforcement Laminate *	Fabrication Method
A	63,5	0,43	$[(\pm 45)_{wg}/\text{FM300}]$	Machined
B1-B2	76,2-63,5	0,28	$[(45/90/-45/0)_c/\text{FM300}]$	Machined
C1-C2	76,2-63,5	0,38	$[2(\pm 45)_{wg}]$	Machined
D1-D2	76,2-63,5	0,31	$[2(\pm 45)_{wg}/\text{EPK9340}]$	Bonded
E	63,5	0,13	$[4(\pm 45)_{wg}/\text{EPK9340}]$	Bonded

(*) wg: woven E-glass/epoxy ; c: carbon/epoxy ; FM300: film adhesive; EPK9340: adhesive

Two approaches were used to fabricate the specimens. The first five were cut from a laminated composite plate of the required stacking sequence, i.e. the arm reinforcement laminates were co-cured on top and bottom of the cross-ply sublaminates. A numerically controlled milling machine was used to cut the specimen outlines and to reduce the thickness of the central section (gauge area) down to the FM300 film adhesive guarding against damaging the mid-plane sublaminates. This solution has been proven effective since the surface of the central gauge area of specimens A thru B2 was found to be free of any major defects. This was not the case for specimens C1 and C2 in which the FM300 film adhesive was not present.

The presence of high residual stresses in the laminated plates having E-glass reinforcement laminates co-cured on the carbon/epoxy sublaminates generated a problem that was first underestimated. The large difference in thermal expansion coefficients of glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy material systems induced in-plane compressive loads acting on the cross-ply sublaminates and resulting in a buckled gauge area. As can be seen in Figure 2, a buckled cross-ply sublaminates adversely affects the mechanical response to applied load of the specimen. It

is worth notice that the above mentioned phenomenon was not as badly observed when a FM300 film adhesive separates the arm reinforcement plies from the mid-plane sublaminates (specimen A).

Specimens D1, D2 and E were obtained by bonding with HYSOL EPK9340 adhesive (room temperature cured) three pre-cut cruciform laminated plates, two of which (top and bottom) incorporated a central window corresponding to the gauge area. There was no need to machine that area. A wide variety of specimens, having different arm reinforcement laminates and central gauge area free of any defects can thus be easily produced.

Figure 2. Average laminate stress vs. load for a buckled central gauge area (specimen C2, equibiaxial tension).

Figure 3. Strain gauges' location.

3.0 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Test setup and experimental procedure

The specimens were fully instrumented with 350 Ω strain gauges, as shown in Figure 3. Three-element rosettes were used to measure strains where the magnitude of the shear component is of interest. Uniaxial strain gauges and tee-rosettes were used to measure normal strains at the periphery of the gauge area and far away in the arms.

The specimens were loaded under load-control in a 250 kN servo-hydraulic biaxial-load apparatus described elsewhere in details by Makinde et al. [12]. A loading rate of 0,1 kN/min was adopted throughout the investigation. Loading was stopped at predetermined load levels to measure strain gauges output.

The specimens were first loaded at low load level under different biaxial tension ratios ($K=q_2/q_1$) ranging from $K=0$ to ∞ to study their mechanical behaviour. Three specimens, namely A, C1 and D1, were then loaded up to failure under equibiaxial tension to assess their performance in view of evaluating the biaxial static strength of the material under study.

3.2 Analysis and results

3.2.1 analysis

The mechanical stresses in the material were computed from the measured strains using the classical laminated plate theory. Material properties were taken as shown in Table 2. The applied stresses (far-field stress) at the arms were computed as follows :

$$q_i = \frac{P_i}{2 * HAW * T_a} ; i=1,2 \quad (1)$$

where P_i were the applied loads.

Table 2. Material properties.

Property	Material system			
	AS4/3501-6	E-Glass/Epoxy	E-Glass/Epoxy (woven)	Epoxy Resin
h_0 (mm)	0,140	0,220	0,240	0,12-0,24
Q_{xx} (GPa)	138,8	39,16	23,77	2,64
Q_{yy} (GPa)	9,013	8,392	23,77	2,64
Q_{xy} (GPa)	2,704	2,182	2,19	0,79
Q_{ss} (GPa)	7,1	4,14	4,14	0,92

3.2.2 Stress-strain response of the specimens

Figure 4 shows typical stress versus applied load curves (average laminate stresses) as computed from the strain readings at gauge point 1 and 5 for $K=0,25$ and 1. As can be seen, the normal stress components $\bar{\sigma}_1$ and $\bar{\sigma}_2$ in the central gauge area are always higher than in the fillet and the shear stress component $\bar{\sigma}_6$ is always close to or equal to zero, therefore indicating that biaxial stress-strain conditions exist in the gauge area. Although not shown in this Figure, the magnitude of $\bar{\sigma}_6$ is somewhat higher at gauge point 2 thru 4 but still negligible as compared to the magnitude of the normal stress components (see Table 4). Relatively high shear stresses develop in the fillets joining the arms. This tendency has been predicted by the FE analysis.

Figure 5 shows the variation of the biaxial stress field developed in the central gauge area of the specimen as a function of the applied biaxial loading for $0 \leq K \leq 1$. Hence the load to be applied at the specimen arms to produce any desirable state of stress in the central gauge area can be easily determined from this Figure. As a general rule, the stiffer the annulus surrounding the gauge area is, the greater K has to be to compensate for Poisson's effect of the specimen. For example, a small gauge area diameter and a thick arm reinforcement laminate will both contribute to the stiffness of the surrounding annulus. Indeed the highest K is for specimen E ($T_g/T_a=0,13$) while K is higher for B2 ($GAD=63,5$ mm) as compared to specimen B1 ($GAD=76,2$ mm). As can be seen, uniaxial state of stress can be obtained in the central gauge area for K ranging from 0,18 to 0,40. Similar response curves can be plot for strain ratios.

3.2.3 Stress-strain uniformity in the gauge area

Figure 6 shows typical stress versus load curves for the normal stress components $\bar{\sigma}_1$ and $\bar{\sigma}_2$ at gauge points 1 thru 4. As can be seen, the magnitude of the computed stresses vary from one point to another in a relatively narrow range. In the case shown herein, this range is bound by the value of $\bar{\sigma}_1$ at gauge point 1 and that of $\bar{\sigma}_1$ at gauge point 4. This indicates the stress-strain field in the central gauge area is not fully homogeneous.

Figure 4. Average laminate stress in the central gauge area (G1) and in the fillet (G5) for various load biaxiality ratios $K=q_2/q_1$ (specimen B1).

Figure 5. Experimental average laminate stress ratio in the gauge area vs. load biaxiality ratio.

Figure 6. Biaxial stresses in the gauge area computed at G1 thru G4 (specimen B1, $K=1$).

To quantify the homogeneity of the stress field in the gauge area, a uniformity criterion has been defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_1 &= \% \text{ of surface where } 1 - \delta \leq \bar{\sigma}_1 / \bar{\sigma}_{1c} \leq 1 + \delta \\
 H_2 &= \% \text{ of surface where } 1 - \delta \leq \bar{\sigma}_2 / \bar{\sigma}_{2c} \leq 1 + \delta \\
 H_3 &= \% \text{ of surface where } 1 - \delta \leq (\bar{\sigma}_2 / \bar{\sigma}_1) / (\bar{\sigma}_{2c} / \bar{\sigma}_{1c}) \leq 1 + \delta
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{1c}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{2c}$ are the normal stress components in the center of the gauge area and δ is a tolerance parameter that controls the criterion severity. This three-value-criterion guarantees that, in a given area percentage, $\bar{\sigma}_1$ and $\bar{\sigma}_2$ are almost constant and their magnitude are related by the same biaxiality ratio. Table 3 shows the values of this criterion for six specimens with three different values of δ based on stresses evaluated by the FE analysis. The two first values H_1 and H_2 are equal since $K=1$ in the cases considered herein. δ_{max} corresponding to each H_i of the criterion is the value of the tolerance parameter for which H_i equals 100%.

From Table 3, one can see that a uniformity criterion with $\delta=0,05$ is extremely severe, the surface percentage satisfying this criterion lies generally between 30 and 45%. When $\delta=0,10$ this percentage is 1,7 times higher and doubles for $\delta=0,15$. A plot of this criterion permitted to see that the area where stresses are considered uniform covers a square-like region centered

in the gauge area. These observations have been verified by the experimental results in the four measuring points (G1 thru G4).

Table 3. Stress homogeneity criterion values(%) for $\delta = 0,05; 0,10$ and $0,15$ ($K=1$).

Spec.	H_1, H_2				H_3				H_1, H_2, H_3		
	0,05	0,10	0,15	δ_{max}	0,05	0,10	0,15	δ_{max}	0,05	0,10	0,15
A	74	87	96	0,18	50	70	89	0,25	46	70	89
B1	65	80	87	0,25	40	57	69	0,39	32	57	69
B2	72	87	96	0,17	47	69	88	0,24	40	69	88
C1	62	75	82	0,30	35	50	64	0,49	29	45	63
C2	68	83	95	0,19	42	66	78	0,28	37	65	78
E	65	81	93	0,21	40	60	74	0,32	31	57	74

3.2.4 Performance of specimens for tests up to failure

Table 4 shows values of the average laminate stresses as computed from the measured experimental strains in both the central gauge area and in the fillet joining the arms for an applied equibiaxial stress of 125 MPa.

Table 4. Average laminate stresses(MPa) computed at gauge points 1 thru 5 ($q_1=q_2=125$ MPa).

Spec.	G1			G2			G3			G4			G5		
	$\bar{\sigma}_1$	$\bar{\sigma}_2$	$\bar{\sigma}_6$												
A	239	224	0,4	221	192	3,8	216	238	4,2	216	225	-1,6	104	111	-37
B1	256	247	2,1	240	226	8,0	234	255	0,2	225	238	-6,7	124	123	-67
B2	222	230	-1,9	207	207	1,0	217	246	1,9	219	209	-2,8	125	120	-52
D1	264	282	7,3	284	255	5,7	238	286	8,2	278	262	-1,2	99	102	-43
D2	322	302	-1,2	289	261	8,1	243	297	3,9	276	271	3,1	109	109	-43
E	395	360	-10,7	392	322	-9,1	313	352	-4,3	381	390	-15,7	99	87	-53

As can be seen, the shear component is always negligible in the central area, as compared to the normal components $\bar{\sigma}_1$ and $\bar{\sigma}_2$. The average normal stress components are always higher in the central gauge area than in the fillet (gauge point 5) by a factor of 2 approximately and by a factor of 3 for specimen E therefore showing dependency to the T_g/T_a ratio. Although no absolute rule relates the test area diameter and the magnitude of the average laminate stresses in the gauge area, the trend is that the stresses are higher for a test area of 76,2 mm of diameter. This can easily be understood since the wider annulus surrounding a 63,5 mm diameter test area is stiffer and shares greater load. A similar trend can be observed for the stresses in the fillet radii (gauge point 5).

Among all, specimen E is the one that has reached the highest stress level in the central gauge area for an applied equibiaxial load of 125 MPa. The stress level in the central gauge area of specimen E is approximately 1,6 times higher than for any other specimens having the same GAD. Therefore, for a given load, a lower T_g/T_a value will lead to higher stresses in the center.

The magnitude of the average laminate shear stress is fairly high in the fillet (gauge point 5), i.e. approximately 0,4 to 0,5 times the magnitude of the normal components. This transforms into ply stresses high enough to cause premature failure of the 0° and 90° plies ($\sigma_x; \sigma_y; \sigma_s = 440; 36; 42$ MPa, for instance in specimen D2). Indeed, by simple linear extrapolation, and knowing the ply shear and transverse strengths are of the order of 93 MPa and 52 MPa respectively for AS4/3501-6, it can be seen that those plies will suffer matrix cracking and fail in shear well before the longitudinal strength is reached, therefore causing arm tear-off. Since the numerical analysis has shown that extremely high shear stresses exist near the free edge of the fillet, it is unlikely that failure in the gauge area can occur before specimen failure. Three specimens, namely A, C1 and D1, were loaded up to failure to verify this last assumption and to determine the magnitude of the stresses induced in the gauge area at maximum load.

Table 5. Experimental ply stress(MPa) and strain(%) values at specimen failure for K=1.

Spec.	0° and 90° plies (G1)						0° and 90° plies (G5)						±45° plies (G5)		
	σ_x	σ_y	σ_s	ϵ_x	ϵ_y	ϵ_s	σ_x	σ_y	σ_s	ϵ_x	ϵ_y	ϵ_s	σ_x	σ_y	σ_s
A	1230	102	2,8	0,869	0,871	0,039	989	84,1	-116	0,699	0,723	±1,63	8,71	360	1,03
C1	888	86	6,1	0,625	0,764	0,086	702	67,6	-87,6	0,494	0,602	±1,23	9,11	275	4,48
D1	1110	100	31,2	0,778	0,877	0,439	870	74,6	-96,3	0,614	0,644	±1,36	16,9	309	1,23

Table 5 shows values of the ply stresses at the center of the gauge area as well as in the fillet joining the arms for the above mentioned specimens loaded to failure (applied load at failure: 344 MPa for A, 283 MPa for C1 and 277 MPa for D1). In all cases, premature failure initiating in the fillets was observed, as expected. Although none of the three specimens failed in the central gauge area, fairly high stresses (strains) were attained in the center giving a failure index of the order of 3 to 5 based on the Tsai-Hill criterion, hence indicating that rupture of the cross-ply sublaminates in the gauge area would have occurred in an earlier loading stage. It has to be recognized that the major contribution to this high failure index value comes from σ_y . However, σ_x was as high as 0,85 times the longitudinal ply strength, therefore indicating that rupture in the central gauge area would be possible once solving the shear problem in the fillet through improved geometry and laminate composition.

4.0 CONCLUSIONS

Eight cruciform shaped specimens were fabricated and tested under biaxial loading conditions to experimentally investigate the effect of GAD and arm reinforcement laminate (type of reinforcement and thickness ratio) on their behaviour. It was found that a successful specimen design was not only a reflection of the design itself but also of the procedures used to fabricate it. Two fabrication methods produced specimens with very little defects -if any- in the central gauge area and will be retained for further investigations: a) assembling specimens by bonding pre-cut laminates and b) reducing the thickness of the gauge area using a CNC milling machine when an adhesive film separates the mid-plane sublaminates from the arm reinforcement laminates.

Finite element as well as experimental results confirmed that biaxial stress-strain conditions exist in the circular gauge area of the specimens with the shear component being close to or equal to zero. A numerical analysis using the finite element method showed that the biaxial stress-strain field is homogeneous over 70% of the gauge area in the best cases for $\delta = 0,10$.

Among the two central gauge area diameter chosen for this investigation, a diameter of 63,5 mm gives larger homogeneous stress-strain field but smaller stress (strain) normal components in the cross-ply sublaminates (test material). An optimum gauge area dimension has thus to be found. The arm reinforcement laminate (nature and thickness ratio) has great influence on the homogeneity of the stress field in the central gauge area and can lead to increased stresses in the center by as much as 1,6 times.

High shear stresses develop in the fillet joining the arms and cause premature failure of the specimen. However relatively high stresses were measured in the central gauge area at specimen's failure load. This indicates the specimen concept is good in view of exploring the biaxial static strength of composites but only need to be improved through the knowledge gained in this study. Future investigations will focus on solving the premature arm failure problem considering reinforcement laminates of different fibre orientations and thickness. The effect of a square gauge area on the stress (strain) field homogeneity and magnitude will also be investigated.

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REFERENCES

1. Liu, A.f. and Yamane, J.R., *Crack Growth Under Equibiaxial Tension*, Res. Mechanica, (5), 1982, 1-11.
2. Chaudonneret, M., Gilles, P., Labourdette, R. and Pollicella, H., *Machine d'essais de traction biaxiale pour essais statiques et dynamiques*, La Recherche Aérospatiale, (5), 1977, 299-305.
3. Wilson, I.M. and White, D.J., *Cruciform Specimen for Biaxial Fatigue Tests: An Investigation Using Finite-Element Analysis and Photoelastic-Coating Techniques*, J. of Strain Analysis, 6(1), 1971, 27-37.
4. Susuki, I., *Biaxial Testing of Composite Laminates Using Cruciform Specimens*, Proc. ICCM8, Honolulu, Hawaii (USA), 1991, 37A1-37A9.
5. Smith, E.W. and Pascoe, K.J., *Biaxial Fatigue of Glass-Fibre Reinforced Composite. Part 1: Fatigue and Fracture Behaviour*, Biaxial and Multiaxial Fatigue, EGF3, 1989, 367-396.
6. Inizan, G., *Endommagement d'une plaque composite trouée, en carbone-époxy, sous chargement biaxial monotone et cyclique*, La Recherche Aérospatiale, (1), 1986, 63-75.
7. Jones, D.L., Poulou, P.K. and Liebowitz, H., *Effect of Biaxial Loads on the Static and Fatigue Properties of Composite Materials*, Multiaxial Fatigue, ASTM STP 858, 1985, 413-427.
8. Daniel, I.M., *Biaxial Testing of $[0_2/\pm 45]_s$ Graphite/Epoxy Plates with Holes*, Experimental Mechanics, 22(5), 1982, 188-195.
9. Ellyin, F., Lefebvre, D. and Neale, K.W., *High Strain Biaxial Fatigue of 2024-T351 Aluminium Under Combined Axial Stress and Torsion*, Advances in Materials Technology in the Americas-1980, ASME, (2), 1980, 17-21.
10. Swanson, S.R., Christoforou, A.P. and Colvin, G.E. jr., *Biaxial Testing of Fiber Composites Using Tubular Specimen*, Experimental Mechanics, 28(3), 1988, 238-243.
11. Krempf, E. and Niu, T.M., *Graphite/Epoxy $[\pm 45]_s$ tubes. Their Fatigue Behaviour Under Completely Reversed Load Controlled Loading*, J. of Composite Materials, (16), 1982, 172-187.
12. Makinde, A., Thibodeau, L., Lefebvre, D., Neale, K.W. and Lahoud, A.E., *Development of a Servohydraulic Machine for Testing Cruciform Specimens*, Proc. of the 1989 SEM Spring Conference on Experimental Mechanics, Cambridge (USA), 1989, 112-116.